

Extended Data:

Carbon and nitrogen uptake through photosynthesis and feeding by photosymbiotic Acantharia

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Extended Data - Tables and Figures

Extended Data Table 1. Information on RCC cultures used in this study.

Algal strain:	RCC 178	RCC 1383 / CCMP2495	RCC 1521	RCC 307
Species	<i>Isochrysis galbana</i> *	<i>Phaeocystis cordata</i>	<i>Effrenium voratum</i> (<i>Symbiodinium voratum</i>)	<i>Synechococcus</i> sp.
Class	Prymnesiophyceae	Prymnesiophyceae	Dinophyceae	Cyanophyceae
Division	Haptophyta	Haptophyta	Alveolata	Cyanophyta
ESD	5 µm	4 µm	10 µm	1 µm
Ocean	Atlantic Ocean	Mediterranean Sea	Mediterranean Sea	Mediterranean Sea
Sampling site	Britanny coast - Caen	Gulf of Naples	Gulf of Naples	lat:39.17; long:6.17
Original isolation date	12/02/1988	15/03/1991	Unknown	Unknown
Growth temperature	19.5 °C	19.5 °C	19.5 °C	19.5 °C

* Strain has recently been re-identified as *Tisochrysis lutea*.

Extended Data Table 2. Nutrient conditions of growth medium and in the surface waters of the Mediterranean Sea. Concentrations are in μM unless otherwise indicated. For natural seawater, the data for macronutrients correspond to an average over three years at the sampling site of our study (at Villefranche-sur-Mer available at <https://www.somlit.fr/>).

		K/2	K/5-6	Med. Sea water *	
Compound		growth	growth	min	max
		medium	medium		
Macro nutrients	NaNO_3	288	100	4.38×10^{-2}	1.02
	NH_4Cl	5	5	2.01×10^{-3}	1.12×10^{-1}
	NaH_2PO_4	18	6.25	7.92×10^{-2}	3.03×10^{-1}
	(Na)FeEDTA	5.85	5.85		
	$\text{Na}_2\text{EDTA} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	50	50		
	$\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.0026	0.0026		
Trace metal solution	$\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.04	0.04	4.21×10^{-4}	5.27×10^{-3}
	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.025	0.025	1.7371×10^{-5}	3.78×10^{-4}
	$\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.45	0.45		
	H_2SeO_3	0.005	0.005		
	$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.00314	0.00314	1.00×10^{-5}	1.51×10^{-4}
Vitamin solution	Vit. B12	0.37 nM	0.37 nM		
	Biotin	2.0 nM	2.0 nM		
	Thiamine HCL	0.3	0.3		

* $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ instead of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and NiCl_2 instead of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Extended Data Table 3. Results of Tukey Kramer HSD post-hoc test for all possible comparisons of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in Acantharia incubations with inorganic nutrients. The most relevant comparisons are highlighted in bold, these entail the comparisons of each treatment with its natural control and the comparisons between the enrichment treatments.

Treatment	vs	Treatment	Difference	Std Err Dif	Lower CL	Upper CL	p-Value	Conclusion
15NO3		Dark	112.40	13.92	66.67	158.13	<.0001	Significant difference
15NO3		14NH4 control	111.19	13.02	68.41	153.97	<.0001	Significant difference
15NO3		12C control	108.88	13.02	66.10	151.66	<.0001	Significant difference
15NO3		14NO3 control	108.11	13.92	62.38	153.84	<.0001	Significant difference
13C		Dark	72.93	13.02	30.15	115.70	0.0004	Significant difference
13C		14NH4 control	71.72	12.06	32.11	111.32	0.0002	Significant difference
13C		12C control	69.41	12.06	29.80	109.01	0.0003	Significant difference
13C		14NO3 control	68.64	13.02	25.86	111.42	0.0007	Significant difference
15NH4		Dark	56.81	12.45	15.91	97.72	0.0033	Significant difference
15NH4		14NH4 control	55.60	11.44	18.03	93.18	0.0018	Significant difference
15NO3		15NH4	55.59	12.45	14.68	96.49	0.0041	Significant difference
15NH4		12C control	53.29	11.44	15.72	90.87	0.0027	Significant difference
15NH4		14NO3 control	52.52	12.45	11.62	93.43	0.0071	Significant difference
15NO3		13C	39.47	13.02	-3.31	82.25	0.0824	No Significant difference
13C		15NH4	16.12	11.44	-21.46	53.69	0.7908	No Significant difference
14NO3 control		Dark	4.29	13.92	-41.45	50.02	0.9999	No Significant difference
12C control		Dark	3.52	13.02	-39.26	46.30	1	No Significant difference
14NO3 control		14NH4 control	3.08	13.02	-39.70	45.86	1	No Significant difference
12C control		14NH4 control	2.31	12.06	-37.30	41.92	1	No Significant difference
14NH4 control		Dark	1.21	13.02	-41.57	43.99	1	No Significant difference
14NO3 control		12C control	0.77	13.02	-42.01	43.55	1	No Significant difference

Extended Data Figure 1. Light (Rottermann Contrast) microscopy photographs taken after an experimental incubation. White arrows indicate a pseudopodal extension of each cell, and cyan arrows the limitations of the Acantharia ectoplasm

Extended Data Figure 2. Conceptual drawing of experiments to assess carbon and nitrogen uptake rates. Pulse Amplitude Modulated (PAM) fluorometer measurements were performed on several Acantharia each day before and after incubations. Each illuminated treatment was accompanied by a similar incubation using non-enriched nutrients, which is not depicted.

Extended Data Figure 3. Conceptual drawing of experiments for assessment of acantharian grazing rates estimation by cell counts (prey disappearance, as performed on each algal culture. Samples for algal cell density at 0 h were taken from the initial culture at step 1.

Extended Data Figure 4. Example images made using a CCD camera for Microscopy Pulse-Amplitude-Modulation fluorescence analysis and ImagingWIN software, and a boxplot showing maximal quantum yield (F_v/F_m) of Acantharia measured before incubation (0 h, $n = 86$) and after incubation (4 h, $n = 90$). The colour scale applies for the F_0 and F_m images to indicate fluorescence signal intensity. The F_v/F_m image is scaled to F_m to give a 3-D impression and better show out of focus objects. A near infrared (NIR) image take under minimal light illumination is shown to illustrate the entire cell. The region of interest of which fluorescence values were obtained is encircled in each image (*i.e.* the central capsule).

Extended Data Figure 5. Non-symbiotic Acantharia after incubation with LFLA *I. galbana* at different time points imaged using confocal microscopy. Panels show the snapshots of different time points (30 and 240 min) with 3-D projections of separate channels and a composite of channels 1 through 3. Channel 1 (cyan) is for emission wavelengths 460-472 nm (Celltracker Blue fluorescence), and channel 2 (yellow) for 603-635 nm (unknown autofluorescence, likely carotenoids), and channel 3 (magenta) for 693-782 nm (chlorophyll autofluorescence). Channel 4 represents transmission light images. Z-stack images were three-dimensionally reconstructed with Imaris software.

Extended Data Supplementary Experiments - Methodology and Results

Acantharia and acantharian swarmer barcoding

Five single-cell Acantharia samples, as well as in triplicate acantharian swarmers were collected in 98% EtOH for barcoding. DNA extraction and purification were done using a Masterpure DNA purification kit (Epicentre-Illumina) following the manufacturer's protocol. Single-cell Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) was done to amplify the 28S ribosomal DNA gene with specific primers for Acantharia, '28S_Rad2' (5'-TAA GCG GAG GAA AAG AAA-3') and 'ITS a3' (5'-TCA CCA TCT TTC GGG TCC CAA CA-3') as described in Decelle et al., 2012. The 28S gene for Acantharia was amplified in a total volume of 25 μ L with: 0.35 μ M of each primer, MgCL2 1.5 mM, dNTPs mix 0.4 μ M, buffer GoTaq 1x and 0.625u of GoTaq Flexi polymerase G2 (Promega). The reaction proceeded with the following PCR parameters: 5 min at 95 $^{\circ}$ C, followed by 35 cycles of 30 s denaturation at 95 $^{\circ}$ C, 30 s annealing at 53-55 $^{\circ}$ C, 2 min extension at 72 $^{\circ}$ C, with a final elongation step of 10 minutes at 72 $^{\circ}$ C. All amplification products have been purified using the kit Nucleospin PCR Clean-Up (Macherey-Nagel) and eluted with 22 μ L of NE buffer. Sequencing was done using Big Dye Terminator Cycle Sequencing Kit (Life Technologies) by Macrogen. Sequences were cleaned and contigs constructed using ChromasPro software. Contig sequences were deposited under Genbank accession numbers OK157864-OK157871.

All resulting 28S contig sequences constituted the same sequence, with the best NCBI blast result identified as *Acanthostaurus* sp. or *Acanthometra* sp..

Extended Data Figure 6. Preliminary experiment acantharia isotopic composition.

Evolution of isotopic carbon composition of Acantharia at different sampling times (4 h; 24 h) with two N sources treatment (blue: NH_4^+ ; red NO_3^-) (n = 3 each). Controls (n = 7 each) are the combination of the control (non-enriched) treatments at all the time points (0 h; 4 h; 24 h). Incubations were performed in 0.025 μM $^{15}\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ or 0.12 μM $\text{Na}^{15}\text{NO}_3$ and 10 μM $\text{NaH}^{13}\text{CO}_3$, with Acantharia specimens obtained in September 2018 from the bay of Villefranche-sur-Mer. Further methodology is as described in the main text, except that incubations were performed in glass bottles in 50 ml volume, and under low (room level) illumination (undetermined, estimated at 20 to 35 photons $\text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ by reference). Shown are mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values \pm SE. Isotope ratios suggests more carbon fixation in the presence of NH_4^+ .

Extended Data Figure 8. Isotopic nitrogen composition for two Collodaria morphotypes after 5 hours of incubation in either the light or dark with dissolved $\text{NaH}^{13}\text{CO}_3$ ($30 \mu\text{M}$) and $^{15}\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ ($0.2 \mu\text{M}$). Specimens were obtained in April 2019 from the bay of Villefranche-sur-Mer using the methodology as described in the main text. Shown are mean $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values \pm SE in ‰. The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of control incubations (incubated with non-enriched solutions) is indicated with dashed lines. Oneway-ANOVA with Tukey-Kramer post hoc test was conducted to compare the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ among treatments, for this the natural samples (both dark and light) were combined. For morphotype A the combined samples of natural incubation average $0.97 \pm 0.26\text{‰}$ and is significantly different from $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ after incubation with enriched nutrients in both light ($51.41 \pm 2.43\text{‰}$) and dark ($46.51 \pm 1.92\text{‰}$) incubations ($F_{2,5} = 151.6$, $p < 0.0001$). In the case of morphotype B a similar trend is seen but with a smaller change in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$. After 5 hours both dark ($35.76 \pm 4.93\text{‰}$) and light incubation ($30.94 \pm 4.75\text{‰}$), $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ has increased significantly from the natural situation ($3.18 \pm 0.19\text{‰}$, $F_{2,5} = 12.45$, $p = 0.011$). This shows nitrogen uptake is significant in both morphotype A and B independent of light or dark conditions.

Extended Data Figure 7. Acantharian $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (A.bottom) and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (A.top) in control samples containing unlabelled *I. galbana* (non-enriched) and after dark incubation with labelled *I. galbana* (enriched) are shown in the graph. Uptake of carbon and nitrogen from isotopically labelled algal prey is indicated in the side table (B) for each individual sample.

I. galbana cultures were enriched with $95 \mu\text{M }^{13}\text{C}$; $0.12 \mu\text{M }^{15}\text{NO}_3^-$; $0.02 \mu\text{M }^{15}\text{NH}_4^+$ for 24 h. The enriched cultures were, and rinsed with FSW three times to clean the cells of enriched medium. The rinsed cells were re suspended in FSW 3 h before being used as potential prey. Forty to fifty Acantharia were incubated per sample, for 4 h in the dark (to prevent ^{13}C uptake by the acantharian algal symbionts) together with 10 mL of heavy isotope enriched prey culture. The prey were simultaneously incubated without Acantharia and under the same condition to allow calculations of algal C and N uptake. After incubation, the samples were prepared for isotopic analysis as in the main text.